

International Cooperation to Enhance University Education Quality - A Perspective from Nam Can Tho University

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ABSTRACT: In the context of globalization, improving the quality of education has become one of the top priorities for universities. International cooperation not only helps educational institutions improve their curricula but also expands opportunities for students to access knowledge and experiences from advanced education systems worldwide. This article presents suggestions to strengthen international cooperation aimed at improving the quality of education from the practical perspective of Nam Can Tho University.

Keywords: International Cooperation, Education Quality, Quality Improvement, Nam Can Tho University.

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1. Introduction

The prosperity of every nation is closely intertwined with the development of higher education, and vice versa. Higher education reflects a nation's intellectual level, serves as the scientific and technological foundation for economic development, and provides a pool of talented individuals for social advancement. The deepening process of globalization and the rise of the knowledge economy have had a profound impact on all aspects of society. Globalization has presented nations with both significant opportunities and challenges for development and international integration. In this context, higher education, with its function of cultivating intellectual and creative human resources and disseminating knowledge, has become a driving force for national development. The post-World War II "rise" of East Asian economies such as Japan, South Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and Singapore has demonstrated the critical role of highly qualified human resources in economic development and the importance of university-led national development.

International cooperation has long been an integral part of university missions. However, as globalization has intensified over the past two decades, this activity has become a means for higher education to proactively meet the demands of globalization in the present and future. International integration for Vietnam in the coming period is essentially a higher stage of international cooperation. Enhancing international cooperation and internationalization in all aspects, including education, scientific research, quality assurance,

and quality assessment, at Nam Can Tho University contributes to building a foundation for international integration in global education for higher education in Vietnam.

2. The Essential Role of International Cooperation in Higher Education

In the trend of global integration, international cooperation has become an indispensable factor in the development strategy of universities, especially higher education institutions. The goal of this cooperation is to improve the quality of education and research, attract resources, and enhance the prestige of universities. The Vietnamese government has also set clear goals for improving the quality of higher education, international integration, and training high-quality human resources. Vietnam has been paying great attention to this issue for many years, as evidenced by the Politburo's issuance of Resolution 22-NQ/TW on international integration and the establishment of the National Steering Committee on International Integration, chaired by the Prime Minister. Resolution 22-NQ/TW clearly states that economic integration is the spearhead, but the Vietnamese government also always affirms its determination to bring Vietnam to deep international integration in all aspects of socio-economic-political-cultural life. However, for a developing country like Vietnam, integration not only brings opportunities but also disadvantages and challenges. The education sector, an important sector that directly affects the building of human resources and is a key factor in developing a knowledge-based economy, is of course no exception. In this article, the authors initially analyze the education situation in Vietnam in general and Nam Can Tho University (DNC) in particular. At the same time, pointing out the opportunities and challenges, thereby suggesting some solutions for higher education on the path of international integration.

In the current context of globalization, strengthening international cooperation in higher education in Vietnam is an objective requirement. This stems from two fundamental reasons:

Firstly, the opening-up of education in various countries demands that universities implement and develop international cooperation activities. Globalization trends and the explosion of science and technology have been driving higher education institutions in each country to continuously innovate and progress, especially through international integration to quickly update new trends and knowledge. In a world undergoing constant change with increasing challenges, the heavy responsibility of education in general and higher education in particular is to provide a high-quality workforce to adapt, survive, and thrive in a fiercely competitive environment. To successfully fulfill this mission, universities need to have global capabilities with international relationships in various forms. To develop in line with the trends of modern higher education worldwide and to narrow the gap between Vietnamese education and the world, universities in Vietnam need to seize opportunities for international cooperation to rub shoulders, compete, self-assess their capabilities, and have the motivation to develop towards greater advancement.

Secondly, in today's highly competitive education market, international cooperation is essential for universities to enhance their competitiveness. Globalization drives market economies, creating numerous opportunities for the development of higher education in more

diverse and profound ways. Today, not only are there public education systems, but also the involvement of private sectors. As a result, education has become a commercialized and internationalized service. Through the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS), the World Trade Organization (WTO) considers education as a service in commercial activities. The internationalization of higher education places domestic universities in a position where they must compete not only with each other but also with foreign universities. Many countries with developed education systems such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, and Singapore are known as potential education export markets, taking their education beyond national borders and attracting hundreds of thousands of international students. In this context, Vietnamese universities must now compete not only with each other in attracting students but also with international universities. This demands that Vietnamese universities develop diverse educational programs and enhance the quality of their training to meet international standards in order to survive and thrive in the long term.

International cooperation in education, particularly at the university level, is manifested in various activities and generally includes the following main forms:

(i) Jointly organizing scientific conferences and workshops, both domestically and internationally. Conducting joint research and organizing international conferences and workshops is one of the ways to leverage intellectual potential.

(ii) Exchange of faculty and students: Organizing short-term or long-term exchange programs for faculty and students to study, research, and experience the international academic environment.

(iii) Technology transfer: Establishing joint research centers, cooperating in the commercialization of research results, and technology transfer. Joint research is one of the important forms of international cooperation. Organizing international relations activities aims to enhance the quality of education, scientific research, and integration into numerous scientific and technological programs, projects, and topics of current interest in various fields of mutual concern. This contributes practically to addressing regional and international practical issues and, at the same time, improves the professional capacity of faculty and staff.

(iv) Exploiting scholarship opportunities for students. Annually, hundreds of undergraduate and graduate students receive scholarships from foreign universities, enterprises, and international organizations to study and conduct research at leading universities worldwide. Besides scholarships for studying abroad, domestic scholarship support from foreign agencies and organizations also encourages students, especially those from disadvantaged backgrounds, to strive for academic excellence.

In the context of increasing globalization, the internationalization of education has become a crucial goal for schools, educational institutions, and training organizations. Internationalization is not merely about attracting international students but also involves enhancing education quality, creating a multicultural learning environment, and strengthening students' competitiveness in the global job market. Of course, to successfully implement the strategy of developing a knowledge-based economy in Vietnam, higher education plays a particularly important role. Educational institutions need to actively implement

internationalization programs and activities to help students improve their learning quality, expand career opportunities, and integrate into the global labor market.

3. International Cooperation in Education at Nam Can Tho University

3.1. Achievements

In recent years, Vietnam has continuously improved its legal framework to promote international cooperation in higher education. The amended Law on Higher Education of 2018 and Decree 86/2018/ND-CP have created a significant legal foundation, enhancing the autonomy of higher education institutions in cooperating with foreign partners. Specifically, these legal documents have clearly defined the conditions and procedures for international joint training programs, scientific research cooperation, and technology transfer. At the same time, they encourage universities to expand international cooperation to improve the quality of training, scientific research, and technology transfer.

For higher education institutions in general and Nam Can Tho University in particular, the role of international cooperation in education is specifically manifested in the following aspects:

Firstly, international cooperation plays a crucial role in attracting foreign investment to develop training and research activities at higher education institutions. Throughout their development, higher education institutions worldwide require significant financial resources to implement practical activities (Phan Phuoc Hien 2019). Both government and institutional funding often face limitations, and international cooperation offers a gateway to increase financial resources through development aid, international grants, concessional loans, research collaboration agreements, and joint training programs.

Secondly, international cooperation is essential in building and enhancing the capacity of faculty and staff working in higher education institutions. Faculty and staff are the determining factor in the quality of higher education. International cooperation not only helps them improve their professional expertise but also develops soft skills, teamwork, and effective communication skills. These elements are crucial in the modern educational environment, where creativity and innovation are mandatory. Moreover, through cooperation, higher education systems in different countries have the opportunity to exchange, learn from management experiences, and share pedagogical expertise. This process allows both parties to enhance their management capabilities and the professional qualifications of their faculty (Associate Professor, PhD. Tran Thi Minh Tuyet 2022). Another practical benefit is that higher education cooperation significantly contributes to strengthening diplomatic relations between countries. Through enhanced international cooperation and effective operation, higher education in DNC is gradually improving, particularly in updating training programs to meet regional and international standards, motivating faculty and staff, and ensuring quality assurance.

Thirdly, through international cooperation activities, Nam Can Tho University can gain valuable experiences in renewing thinking, management methods in education, selecting orientations, improving the training system and processes, combining scientific research with teaching, and simultaneously knowing how to seize opportunities and advantages to gradually narrow the gap between Vietnamese education and the world. In addition, this activity creates conditions for the university to develop sustainably, provide a high-quality workforce, and establish diverse and rich forms of cooperation with various programs, training cooperation projects, scientific research cooperation, bilateral and multilateral cooperation... In this process, universities have seized opportunities, sought the help of international friends, updated scientific and technological advances through joint research programs, linked with foreign partners to gradually standardize training programs and innovate teaching methods, and researched international standards in order to move towards the internationalization of training programs.

Fourthly, the development of international cooperation activities directly impacts the enhancement of the quality of teaching and research activities, as well as the status and prestige of higher education institutions. International cooperation is one of the key criteria for ranking the world's top universities today. With the increasing demand for internationalization, it is impossible to develop without focusing on international cooperation and operating according to international standards to gain recognition and maintain competitiveness in a global environment. An undeniable positive role of international cooperation is to build orientation and innovate education, scientific research, and application to serve the cause of renewal and industrialization, modernization of the country. This process has brought the University of Nam Can Tho valuable experiences in innovating thinking, educational management methods, selecting orientations, and improving training systems and processes, while also approaching more advanced education systems in the world.

Based on meeting the conditions stipulated by the Ministry of Education and Training, the Center for Quality Assurance in Education - Vietnam National University Hanoi has granted a quality assurance certificate for over 14 regular undergraduate programs and 2 master's programs of the university, including: Pharmacy, Business Law, Law, Business Administration, Civil Engineering, Automotive Engineering, Information Technology, Tourism Management, Food Technology, Medical Imaging Engineering, Medical Laboratory Technology, English, Public Relations, Hospitality Management. And 2 master's programs, including: Master of Business Administration and most recently, Master of Business Law. The University of Nam Can Tho is also honored to be ranked among the top 21 educational institutions awarded stars and meeting international standards according to the "University Performance Metrics" (UPM) 4-star rating system (Times Magazine 2023). It can be affirmed that the University of Nam Can Tho has made remarkable efforts in promoting the development of the university's international cooperation activities in general and in the field of training in particular. The university's science and technology activities in recent years have closely followed the national science and technology strategy and are closely linked to the training of high-quality human resources. Many research results have significant theoretical and practical implications, contributing to improving the quality of training at the University. A number of works have achieved good results and have been applied in practice, contributing

to affirming the university's prestige. To promote development and strive to become a standard international university, the University of Nam Can Tho is strengthening international linkages and cooperation with the United States, Japan, New Zealand, South Korea, Malaysia, the Philippines, etc. Many delegations such as the New Zealand Ambassador, the Japanese Consul General, the Philippine Consul General in Vietnam, the US Science Envoy, Regis University (USA), Australian Institute of Business and Technology (AIBT), International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), Tsukui Group (Japan), etc. have visited and cooperated with the university.

The university has welcomed international students for internships and invited foreign lecturers such as Dr. Daniel Wessner, Ms. Elizabeth Holdeman, and Ms. Katherine Lael Larson to collaborate and exchange experiences with our faculty. We have also organized workshops on English teaching skills for high school teachers in Can Tho City, including TESOL courses.

Regarding the internationalization of our programs, the university has initiated several collaborative programs with foreign partners. Notable examples include:

(i) The establishment of the International Medical Faculty: To meet the growing demand for integration in the healthcare sector, Nam Can Tho University launched the International Medical Faculty on June 24, 2024. This faculty will provide education for international students in healthcare programs. Students from countries such as India, Sri Lanka, Nepal, the Middle East, and other regions will be enrolled. With a strong tradition and significant contributions to healthcare workforce development, Nam Can Tho University is recognized as one of Vietnam's leading medical training institutions (Nam Can Tho University 2023). The establishment of the International Medical Faculty marks a significant step forward in the university's internationalization strategy. Committed to training talented doctors and improving healthcare services, the International Medical Faculty continuously innovates and refines its curriculum. Our students are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to address the challenges of the medical field in the 4.0 era, such as precision medicine, artificial intelligence in healthcare, and global health issues.

(ii) The joint Bachelor of Business Administration program: This program is a collaboration between Nam Can Tho University and Malaysia's Multimedia University (MUST). Approved by the Ministry of Education and Training under Decision No. 3712/QD-BGDĐT dated September 22, 2017, the program enables students to develop their English language skills, learn from international lecturers using English-language textbooks, and obtain an IELTS score of 6.5. Additionally, students are equipped with essential skills like CV writing, job interviewing, negotiation, and presentation. Graduates can pursue further studies at both domestic and international institutions.

(iii) The scientific workshop "Cooperation in training & research on semiconductor and electronic technology in the intelligent era" was organized with the aim of exchanging, sharing experiences, and resources on training, infrastructure, practical linkages, and cooperation in training and research between universities and enterprises, in order to promote the training of

high-quality human resources to serve the development of the country's semiconductor and electronics industry" (Nam Can Tho University 2023).

This event marks a significant step forward in promoting research and training high-quality human resources to serve the development of the semiconductor and electronics industry in Vietnam in general, and the Mekong Delta region and Nam Can Tho University in particular. A notable highlight of the workshop is the cooperation between Synopsys (an American electronic design automation company headquartered in Sunnyvale, California, focusing on silicon design and verification, silicon intellectual property, as well as software security and quality. Synopsys provides tools and services for the semiconductor design and manufacturing industry) and DNC in semiconductor human resource training; the remote laboratory system serving microchip design engineering training... This can be seen as a success of DNC in the process of improving training quality to promote high-quality human resource training, contributing to the development of the country's semiconductor and electronics industry in the technology era.

(iv) The signing ceremony of the cooperation agreement between Nam Can Tho University and Champasak University (Lao PDR) has great significance not only for the university but also opens up many opportunities for students, trainees, and lecturers in the field of Tourism and Hospitality Management between the two countries (Nam Can Tho University 2024). Through this, it marks milestones in cooperation and exchange between the two sides to consolidate and enhance knowledge, teaching skills, and scientific research capacity. Besides, Nam Can Tho University will also strive to build and develop, create all conditions to support and connect in the training of human resources of both sides. The signing ceremony contributes to the implementation of fundamental and comprehensive renewal of education and training, including the implementation of the renewal of the general education program towards shifting the focus from one-way knowledge transmission to teaching methods that promote the qualities and abilities of learners (Ministry of Education and Training 2020).

3.2. Limitations

Despite achieving notable results as mentioned above, when compared to the objectives, requirements for integration, and the nature and level of internationalization and cooperation in higher education, Nam Can Tho University still exhibits certain limitations:

Firstly, although international cooperation is no longer unfamiliar to undergraduate programs and is given special attention by the State and university leadership, the process of building a clear strategic mechanism and orientation requires a long time to develop and perfect for implementation. Therefore, international relations have not yet yielded high results. The management mechanism during the period of renewal has undergone many changes in the digital transformation era, and it is still "racing" to adapt to the actual development of the domestic and international training situation.

Secondly, although the leadership has paid great attention to improving the quality of faculty, due to the reality that improving teaching quality requires a lot of time to build and adjust curricula and training programs according to the requirements of the Ministry of

Education, arranging time for faculty to attend full training courses is still very difficult. Staff working in international relations need to improve their expertise, professional skills, and foreign language proficiency. Only then can they effectively exploit information about partners and sources of support from foreign organizations, as well as address working relationships with relevant agencies to improve the quality of training, scientific research, and integration at Nam Can Tho University. The university has not yet fully exploited and taken full advantage of the opportunities from international relations activities.

Thirdly, developing research capacity and absorbing scientific achievements is a key factor determining the sustainable development of higher education. Creating conditions and encouraging innovation in absorbing scientific achievements not only improves the quality of training but also helps prepare a workforce capable of creativity and adaptability in modern society. However, despite significant progress, the process of absorbing scientific achievements in higher education still has many limitations. The application of scientific achievements sometimes becomes mechanical, failing to promote the creativity of both lecturers and students. There are still difficulties in adjusting the application methods to suit the characteristics of each specific subject or course, and it remains dry for both teachers and learners. Scientific achievements are often applied individually, lacking connectivity and integration with traditional teaching methods, leading to low efficiency.

4. Solutions to Enhance the Effectiveness of International Cooperation at Nam Can Tho University

As a multidisciplinary university with a high degree of autonomy, Nam Can Tho University has continuously expanded its international cooperation activities in recent years, achieving significant results and making significant contributions to fulfilling the university's core mission of high-quality education and research. This has increasingly affirmed and enhanced the university's position, role, and prestige on the international stage, while maintaining domestic political security. Adhering to the motto "Quality is the university's honor," the university aims to become a top non-public educational institution in the country by 2025 and a top 20 multidisciplinary university in Vietnam, meeting regional and international standards by 2030.

International cooperation activities not only support education and research but also aim to internationalize curricula and research activities, effectively develop and exploit the intellectual potential of its faculty, gradually integrate with higher education in the region and worldwide, and contribute to strengthening friendship and mutual understanding among nations. Therefore, along with government policies, Nam Can Tho University needs a long-term strategy with specific, feasible programs, plans, and priority orientations to focus on effectively exploiting scientific and educational cooperation with countries and international organizations, serving the university's mission of high-quality education and research. Specifically:

Firstly, a clear international cooperation strategy needs to be developed: defining specific goals, targets, and areas of cooperation. This serves to guide internationalization

efforts and establish the Institution as a model for international cooperation. A specific international cooperation strategy for training should be developed, outlining short-term (3-6 months), medium-term (1-2 years), and long-term (3-5 years) objectives, depending on the organization's planning cycle, funding allocation, project disbursement cycle, or sometimes the term of the institution's operation. Therefore, in terms of the involved workforce, depending on the scale and level of international cooperation activities, specific responsibilities can be assigned to the leadership, a group, or an individual. Additionally, a department or individual can be assigned to support and facilitate tasks according to the outlined strategy. The basic content that staff members should address when developing and implementing an international cooperation strategy includes: the purpose, goals, and outcomes of international cooperation; the reasons for international cooperation; the specific components of international cooperation in training; the timing and duration of implementation; the location and channels for cooperation, and the resources to be utilized.

Secondly, we aim to enhance the qualifications of our teaching and research staff through training and development programs, as well as strengthen international exchange and cooperation in key scientific fields. As our international engagement expands, more of our staff members are traveling to various countries and regions worldwide to work, exchange knowledge, and study in diverse educational fields. These experiences have provided them with invaluable opportunities to enhance their knowledge, expertise, and ability to collaborate with international partners. The practical experience gained from these endeavors is difficult to acquire from textbooks alone. Therefore, on July 22nd, Nam Can Tho University approved Decision No. 136/QĐ-CTHĐT-ĐHNCT, which outlines a plan for the first cohort of staff to pursue doctoral studies. This decision will facilitate the professional development of our faculty. Furthermore, our staff members should take a more proactive and self-directed approach to their learning, actively accumulate and distill their work experiences, and enhance their critical thinking skills as well as their ability to acquire and apply knowledge and practical experience. Additionally, we need to adopt various methods to intensify our research into international issues and cultivate international qualities, continually improving our capacity to interact with the global community.

Thirdly, it is necessary to have a method of absorbing achievements and experiences that is not rigid or mechanical. Experience has shown that no model or method can be right for all countries, all conditions, all circumstances, all fields, or at all stages of history. Therefore, we should not blindly copy or mechanically imitate each other's experiences. Learning from the experiences and methods of other countries requires creativity. Former General Secretary of the Communist Party of Vietnam, Do Muoi, once affirmed: 'When a policy is formed by blindly copying the experiences of foreign countries, lacking independence, autonomy, and creativity, that policy will not be accepted by life and will not succeed' (Dr. Tran Dinh Thang 2013). In the field of higher education, it is the same; we learn from other countries but must apply it to suit the conditions and circumstances of our own country.

5. Conclusion

In the context of increasing globalization, international cooperation in higher education plays a crucial role in enhancing the quality of education, scientific research, and developing human resources for the country. Vietnam has been actively promoting international cooperation in higher education through the establishment of joint training programs, scientific research cooperation, and technology transfer with reputable partners worldwide. However, to fully exploit the potential of international cooperation, long-term investment and commitment from both sides are necessary. This study clarifies that international relations are one of the key tasks contributing to improving the quality of education and scientific research, and are an indispensable condition in the process of international integration. At the same time, international relations also create opportunities for us to take the lead in new information technology and scientific advancements, and to leverage international resources for development. The study also points out the limitations and shortcomings in international relations, thereby proposing measures to overcome these limitations and contribute to improving the effectiveness of international relations at Nam Can Tho University. Overall, international cooperation in higher education is an irreversible trend in the current era. Vietnam needs to continue expanding and promoting international cooperation in higher education, thereby quickly catching up with international standards, enhancing the position and prestige of Vietnamese higher education in general and Nam Can Tho University in particular on the international stage.

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